

Spectrophotometric Studies on Colourless Complexes of Iron (III)

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The colourless complexes formed by Iron (III) with oxalic, malonic and ethylene diamine tetraacetic acids have been studied spectrophotometrically using salicylaldehyde as an auxiliary ligand. Results obtained show that iron (III) forms 1:1 complexes with these carboxylic acids.

IRON (III) has been shown to form a coloured 1:1 complex with salicylaldehyde^{1,2} (SAL) at low pH (~2.0). This suggests the possibility of using SAL as an auxiliary complexing ligand in spectrophotometric investigation of colourless complexes of Iron (III). The present paper describes the use of SAL as an auxiliary ligand in determining the composition of colourless complexes formed by oxalic, malonic and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acids in acid media.

Experimental

Materials: Salicylaldehyde (B.D.H.) was used after distilling by the usual method. Standard reagent solutions were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts of the reagent in 0.01M HNO₃. All other chemicals used were of A. R. quality. The stock Iron (III) solution was prepared as shown earlier³. The stock solutions of carboxylic acids were prepared by dissolving the calculated amount of each in 0.01M HNO₃. Dilute solutions of desired concentrations were obtained as and when needed by diluting the stock solution with 0.01M HNO₃. All aqueous solutions were prepared in water twice distilled over alkaline permanganate.

Apparatus: Absorbance measurements were made on Zeiss-Specol, using 1 cm matched cells. All measurements were carried out at 30° ± 1°.

Results and Discussion

The methods used here have been described earlier by Babko⁴ *et al.* The equilibrium studied may be described as: $\text{FeSAL}^{+2} + n\text{B}^{-m} = \text{FeB}_n^{(3-nm)} + \text{SAL}$ (1) where B^{-m} = carboxylate anion.

$$K_{\text{equil}} = \frac{[\text{FeB}_n^{(3-nm)}][\text{SAL}]}{[\text{FeSAL}^{+2}][\text{B}^{-m}]^n} \quad (2)$$

To determine the composition of iron (III)-carboxylate complexes, these equilibria were studied by two different methods.

In the first method a solution containing FeSAL⁺² (5 × 10⁻⁴ M) was prepared by mixing equal volumes of Iron (III) (1 × 10⁻³ M) and SAL (1 × 10⁻² M) solutions.

The continuous variation⁵ studies were then carried out using 5 × 10⁻⁴ M FeSAL⁺² and 5 × 10⁻⁴ M carboxylic acid solutions. The absorbances were measured at λ_{max} (535nm) of FeSAL⁺².

Two sets of solutions for each equilibrium, one with and the other without carboxylic acid were prepared. The difference in the absorbances of the pair of corresponding solutions for the two sets corresponds to the Y function in the Job's curve. Typical results are shown in Fig. 1 for FeSAL⁺²-oxalic acid system. It can be seen from Fig. 1, that the maximum decolouration was observed at a ratio of iron (III) : oxalic acid = 1:1. This indicates the formation of a complex corresponding to the formula Fe(C₂O₄)⁺ under the experimental conditions used. Similar results were obtained in other systems involving malonic and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acids.

Fig. 1 : Job's curve for FeSAL⁺²-oxalate complex.
Curve A: FeSAL⁺²-0.01M HNO₃.
Curve B: FeSAL⁺²-oxalic acid,
Curve C: Difference of curves A and B.

Fig. 2 : Dependence of decrease in optical density on oxalic acid concentration.

In the alternative method used, sufficient excess of SAL is added so that $[SAL^-]$ in equation (2) may be regarded constant. If the absorbance is not much changed from its initial value then $[FeSAL^{+2}]$ in equation (2) may also be considered approximately constant. Under these conditions, the logarithmic form of the simplified equation (2) will be

$$\log [FeB_n(3-nm)] - n \log [B^{-m}] + C = O \quad (3)$$

The variation in concentration of $[FeB_n(3-nm)]$ is proportional to the decrease in absorbance \bar{D} . In relatively strong acidic solutions ($pH \approx 2$) only a small portion of the added carboxylate is bound to complex, the free carboxylate ion concentration may thus be considered directly proportional to the total concentration of added carboxylic acid. Then the equation (3) may be written as :

$$\log \bar{D} = n \log [B_{total}^{-m}] + C = O \quad (4)$$

If the values of the negative logarithm of the decrease in absorbance and the negative logarithm of carboxylic acid concentration are plotted, then the slope of the curve will correspond to the value of n . Figure 2

shows the results of absorbance measurement of a series of solutions containing Iron (III) (5×10^{-3} mole/liter), a 10-fold excess of SAL (5×10^{-2} mole/liter) and varying amounts of oxalic acid from 0.5×10^{-3} to 2.5×10^{-3} mole/liter. It can be seen from Fig. 2 that the decrease in colour intensity is linearly proportional to the oxalate concentration. From the slope of the linear plot it can be seen that the number of oxalate ions coordinated with iron is 1. Similar results were obtained with malonic acid and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid.

In order to find out if mixed ligand complex formation occurred under the conditions of study, the following test⁶ was done for each equilibrium studied. To a solution containing Iron (III) and excess R, increasing amounts of carboxylic acid were added and the absorbance was measured. The absorbance over the entire visible range was observed to decrease as the concentration of the added carboxylic acid increased. This was interpreted to indicate a progressive conversion of FeR^{+2} to Fe-carboxylate complex. It was concluded therefore that no mixed ligand complexes were formed, atleast under the conditions of present study, in these systems.

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